

LAND RESOURCE AND TENURE INNOVATIONS IN NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Land as a major factor of production and critical resource for economic production is of predominant importance, particularly in agrarian societies. The interest vested on land and attendant resources is further heightened in Nigeria given its high population. This informs the increasing number and magnitude of conflicting interactions arising from access to land and attendant resources which lead to land use disputes in several communities. The study examined land resource and tenure innovations in Nigeria and its implication for agriculture and rural development. Specifically, the study examined the land tenure system, land acquisition and usage as well as tenurial innovation in Nigeria. One hundred and twenty farmers were randomly selected from five communities respectively in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Data were collected, collated and analyzed using means, percentages, and frequency distribution analysis. Findings showed that 85% of the respondents practiced individual land tenure system alone, and this has particular implication on livelihood and household sustenance. The paper suggests a review of land tenure system, reduced cost of procuring farm inputs and improvement in the quality of extension services among others.

Keywords: Agriculture, Land, Land Resource, Land Tenure, Tenure Innovation, Rural Development

Introduction

Societies formed the rules that regulate land tenure in order to control land occupation and ownership, and land tenure system prescribes the way in which a party occupies or holds a piece of land (Timmons, 1943 cited in Eze *et al.* 2011). The enactment of these tenure rules therefore entrench and define land allocation rights.

There is a linkage between land tenure and food security and land plays an important role in the livelihoods of majority of Africans (Ukpong-Umo, 2022). This confirms

that food security and poverty reduction cannot be achieved unless issues of access to land, security of tenure and the capacity to use land productively and in a sustainable manner are addressed. This suggests that land is central in promoting rural livelihoods in Africa because access to land and security of tenure are major in the process through which food security and sustainable development can be realized since the livelihoods of over 70% of the population in Africa are mainly linked to land and natural resources exploitation.

Access to land resources has remained crucial to livelihood and household sustenance particularly in agrarian societies. The control of arable land resource invariably results in conflicts and concomitant food crisis and youth development challenges in Nigeria. Furthermore, individual and community land disputes and attendant conflicts have resulted in destruction of lives, crops and other property (Ukpong-Umo *et al*, 2019).

The type of Land tenure system in operation and nature of property rights laws affect the decision and application of technologies for agricultural and natural resource management. Secured property rights give sufficient incentives to the farmers to increase their efficiencies in terms of productivity and ensure environmental sustainability (Adams, 2001)

This paper examined the land tenure system, land acquisition and usage as well as tenurial innovation in Nigeria

Land, Land Resource and Expression in Nigeria

Land is a high priced resource anywhere, but particularly in agrarian societies which Nigeria is one. As a natural resource in Nigeria, it has multiple expressions through which issues projecting its relevance may be considered (Otto 1998, Ekong, 2010). These expressions according to Ekong (2010), include physical or geographical, spiritual and socio-political. Ekong (2010) further postulates that land as used in the physical or geographical sense refers to a wide variety of natural resource found in a profile from the atmosphere to some metres beneath the soil surface, and it embraces the soil up to root depth, vegetation, fauna (ie animals, insects worms and micro-organisms), water and surface minerals.

The spiritual meaning derives from the rural dwellers' belief that there is a deity in land who acts as a guardian of the earth and man, who must be constantly appeased to avoid her wrath. The socio-political meaning considers land to be synonymous with a

nation of people, a town or community. Thus the expression ‘Yoruba land’ would refer to people within that ethnic/political framework. Land resource may refer to the totality of the earth surface including the area that supports plant and animal life or the earth crust encompassing the biosphere and lithosphere (Ukpong-Umo, 2014). Considering from the legal point of view, Nwanekezie cited in Ukpong-Umo (2014) sees land as any portion of the earth’s surface over which ownership rights can be exercised. These rights, as stressed, relate not just to surface area but also to things such as trees which have been attached by man and to those objects of value that lie either above or below the surface area. Reference to the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999), land is defined as an immovable fixed property, including the physical soil and everything attached to it or chattels real but excluding minerals. Reviewing Ekong (2010) postulation that land as used in the physical or geographical sense refers to a wide variety of natural resource found in a profile from the atmosphere to some metres beneath the soil surface, and embraces the soil up to root depth, vegetation, fauna (i.e., animals, insects, worms and micro-organisms), water and surface minerals. Ukpong-Umo (2014) noted that some communities including those of Oboro and Ibere grand clans in Ikwuano Local Government Area of Abia State; those of Ediene and Obong grand clans in Ikono, Etim Ekpo and Ibiono Ibom Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State as well as Iriebe and Rumuokurushe in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, attach caveat prohibiting land buyers the user-right to certain classified land resources including some species of animals, water bodies and mineral resources as may be found on or under the land area. In other words, the caveat presupposes that a piece of land bought does not confer on the buyer the right to certain other classified resources such as economic trees, animal species, water bodies and minerals that may be found on the land.

Land Tenure System, Land Acquisition and usage in Nigeria

Land tenure may be considered to mean the act of holding, occupying and/ or the right of using land, and as the duration of occupancy (Otto, 1998), but land acquisitions are broadly defined to include not only the purchase of ownership rights but also the acquisition of user rights, for instance through leases or concessions, whether short or long term (Mundiak, 2007). Land tenure system can be defined as the rights and institution that governs access to and use of land, and involves a system of rights, duties and responsibilities concerning the use, transfer, alienation and ownership security of land and its resources. From the ongoing, it is clear that land acquisition and use cannot be discussed extensively without incorporating land tenure system. Land is a veritable ingredient of development especially in the

agricultural and tourism sector of any economy and a fixed resource that cannot be increased with increasing population. Nigeria has a total land mass of 924,768 sq.km with a population of over 200 million and average annual population growth rate of 2.5%, and for such a large number of people who will need land spaces of varying areas for varying purposes, land is an important asset and factor of production for each household. Land acquisition in traditional times came about as humans banded themselves together in search of food, fruits and game and ended up settling in choice areas. There were also cases of conflicts resulting in the dislodgement of band-groups by others with superior power. As bands merged in order to consolidate and reinforce, communities emerged to among others provide wider range of leadership which in turn determine the level of access, right of use and title ownership of land resources. The community then through household leadership began to hold land in trust for the people. Since current land use and allocation rights is determined by the state, the land system is now characterized by several actors including government, community leaders, families, lawyers, middle men and estate agents among others. All activities of the different actors are regulated by the government through policies and programmes. Generally, land systems thrive on clearly stated property rights. Two types of proprietary rights have been defined in literature as absolute or non-derivative interests and derivative interests (Olayemi, 1980). The absolute or non-derivative interests is a non-restrictive access and use of land conferred on the holder. The absolute interest on land has also been explained as inclusive of highest scope of proprietary decisions on the use and management of land. Derivative interest derives from a larger estates or superior estates. The derivative rights cover leaseholds, life interests, mortgage, rents and pledges among others. The two types of property rights (absolute or non-derivative interest and derivative interest) exist in Nigeria.

The Nigerian land system has evolved over the years through precolonial, colonial and postcolonial periods. The three periods are explained below:

1. **Precolonial land ownership structure:** Prior to the colonial era, lands were solely owned by families and communities. The land was owned by the community and held in trust by family heads who then allocate same based on the needs of their subordinates. The legal estate or authority existed at the community or family level. Thus, the leadership of communities and families had absolute interests, while constituents had derivative interests.
2. **Ownership structure during colonial rule:** The ownership of land was regulated by the colonial authorities before independence. The legislations included Treaty of Cession (1861), land proclamation ordinance (1900), land

and native rights act (1947). The colonial legislations were meant to take property rights out of the reach of community leaders. For instance, in 1900, the land proclamation ordinance created by Lord Lugard disregarded the principles of native law and custom and stipulated that the title of land can only be acquired through the high commissioner (Arua and Okorji, 1997).

3. Postcolonial ownership structure: As depicted earlier, the land ownership structure in Nigeria has evolved over the years. Two key legislations have been enacted since independence, namely land tenure law of Northern Nigeria of 1962 and land use act of 1978.

The land tenure law of Northern Nigeria of 1962 stipulated that the minister responsible for land matter controls, holds and allocates land (unoccupied or occupied native lands) to natives of Northern Nigeria. This implies that non-natives except for the approval of the minister could not acquire land titles. The law granted the natives of Northern Nigeria the right to own land for a limited number of years. The individual/native may sell, mortgage or transfer the land subject to the minister's approval.

The land tenure law of 1962 was repealed, and land use decree of 1978 was implemented. Land tenure issues are important components of developmental discourse (Famoriyo, 1980). This is because unplanned or weak regulatory process undermines development as informal settlements grow thereby stressing already inadequate institutional procedure, with high impact on infrastructure, particularly in urban and satellite or sub-urban locations. Therefore, poor land management affects security and growth as it induces slums and sub-optimal living conditions. The Nigerian land use decree of 1978 stipulates that all land belong to the government who holds same in trust for the public. This implies that the government allocates land to individuals and corporate entities based on the objectives of interested parties.

Dale & McLaughlin (2000) observed that small-scale farmers dominate rural landholdings in Nigeria, with average farm size ranging from 0.5 hectre in the south to 4 hectre in the north. About 50% of the Nigerian farms demarcation are less than 1 hectre, while 15% are less than 5 hectre, implying that the Nigerian farm market is dominated by those with small dimension holdings.

Dale & McLaughlin (2000) identified three types of land market in Nigeria as follows:

Formal markets where certificate of occupancy from the government are allocated.

Combination of formal and informal markets where transfer of land rights are certificate of occupancy.

Informal market where the bulk of the transactions are not documented as title owners do not obtain certificate of occupancy.

Land Tenure Improvement and Tenurial Innovation in Nigeria

Land tenure improvement involves the means of redistributing land resources as part of land reform measure in order to achieve the upgrading of informal rights to legally enforceable rights; upgrading of state-issued permits to leases that provide greater protection to the land users; the introduction of provisions for communities to become the legal owners of their traditional land holdings which helps to strengthen land administration system and increase tenure security. This will reduce conflict and make society more stable.

Land resources may refer to the total content of the earth surface including the area that supports plants and animal life, or the earth crust encompassing the biosphere and lithosphere (Feder and Feeny, 1991). Land tenure improvement is an important aspect of any land tenurial innovation programme as it seeks to secure the tenurial status of landholders, farmers and farmworkers (Malinowski, 1935 cited in Ukpong-Umo 2014).

Land tenure improvement if practiced will help to contain land tenure issues including deforestation, degradation of the environment, lowering of carrying capacities of soils, poaching and extinction of wild biotic resources. Land tenure innovations here refer to legalized measures involving government policies and decisions on the best way to bring about some modifications in the existing institutional and structural relationships among citizens in the use and control of land resources (Ekong, 2010). Tenurial innovations involve land reforms and interventions in the prevailing pattern of land ownership, control and usage and the redistribution process in order to change the structure of holdings, improve land productivity and broaden the distribution of benefits.

As earlier indicated, Land tenure may be considered to mean the act of holding, occupying and/ or the right of using land, and as the duration of occupancy (Otto, 1998). This implies that certain privileges, opportunities and claims are conferred on individuals in their use of land. However, it has become apparent that land tenure extends beyond the frontiers of land itself, meaning that there is social interaction that

is central in human relation regarding the use of land and its related resources (Ukpong-Umo, 2014). Barlowe cited in Ukpong-Umo, (2014) opined that land tenure concerns the many different ways in which people, cooperate bodies and governments share in the bundle of land property rights. An arrangement therefore under which people hold, control, occupy and use landed property is referred to as land tenure. This meaning is implicit in the definition of land tenure by Ekong (2003), who sees land tenure as the right to hold, use and possess the natural resources found in the land profile from the atmosphere to some few metres below the soil surface. In the view of Otto (1998), land tenure defines the ways in which individuals gain access to, and acquire rights of use of land either temporary or permanently and the relationship attending such rights. These rights have been categorized as Traditional, Contractual and State tenure systems.

Traditional Tenure System

This system considered as the oldest, may be further sub-divided into groups including allodial and feudal types. In allodial system, land ownership is non-derivative and land is only presumably derived from nature (Otto, 1998), and not inherited from any one in particular. The allodial system was typical of the era of human history and formation where land were acquired as people lay claim to land resources majorly for the purpose of settlement, hunting of games and gathering of fruits. Land at this period of human history was graded alongside water and air which were regarded as having no intrinsic value. It was thereafter that individuals and groups who had access to land bequeathed same to the succeeding generations.

In feudal system, the monarch held land in trust for the people. The Lord manor assists and advises the king on matters of land administration and the Serfs or common people were not allowed access to land. Land tenure in the feudal system consist of a mode where property rights go with a set of social, political, military and economic privileges and obligations (Dabara *et al.*, 2019). The medieval England; the Fulani empire, the Yoruba and Benin-Edo kingdoms in present Nigeria, constitute some vivid example of societies that experienced feudal land tenure system.

Contractual Tenure System

This system involves an arrangement based on valid agreement entered into between concerned parties for the king's consent on a lease, transfer of ownership or outright sales of land. Land that are so contracted have derivative statue. Individuals and communal inheritance may be leased, transferred or sold outright under the contractual arrangement.

State Tenure System

This system applies where all non-derivable rights in land belong to government as mostly found in Socialist States. This system of land tenure may also be found where government of the land have an interest on land matters, therefore in order to re-distribute land for the benefit of citizens, the state intervenes in the prevailing pattern of existing land ownership, control and usage. This case applies in contemporary Nigeria where government had to promulgate the land use decree No. 6 of 1978.

Land everywhere has a variety of usage including agriculture, housing and estate development, infrastructural development, game and forest reserve, parks and zoological garden. In Nigeria where the economy is largely agrarian based, agriculture assumes a large part of the land use and allocation policy, putting all others together on a polar divide. According to Ukpong-Umo, (2014) the average land use and allocation in Nigeria is approximated as follows: agriculture 60%, estate development/housing 10%, infrastructural development 5%, ecological parks, game/forest reserves, wastelands and others 25%.

As alluded to by scholars (Otto, 1998; Ekong, 2003), over 60% of land space in Nigeria is found in rural areas, where the rural population subsist almost only on agriculture. Here, land is the only certainty to continuity at their disposal. Indeed, the overwhelming majority of the rural survival is from the land and what the land has to offer. This is true in that it is from the land that they produce the bulk of food for human and animal consumption, procure raw materials for domestic, commercial and industrial application. On the land and from it, they provide shelter and furniture, along with medicinal valued plant materials for health care as well as grass for grazing their animals, and on the same land they bury their dead, commune and relate with the spirits of their ancestors. As postulated in Otto (1998), the prevailing system of land tenure in Nigeria is seen as constituting the rules and procedures governing the rights, liberties and exposure of groups and individuals in the use and control over the basic resources of land and water.

The traditional land tenure system tend to emphasize group survival rather than individual economic achievement. But currently, communal lands in most Nigerian communities have been fragmentalised resulting in a situation where individual land allotment is barely enough for a person and the family to feed. This arrangement can only support subsistence rather than commercial economy and seen as prohibitive to development. Land is considered as a factor of territorial integrity and so there is a definite reluctance to sell it outright especially to non-natives and those considered as strangers. Where a sale of land is accented, such decision must have the consent of the

extended family members who have hereditary claims on the land. This is because the rights to dispose of land under the traditional tenure system are held by the group and not the individual. In some part of the country however, the right to dispose of land remains usufructuary (i.e., that of use) and not that of alienation in whatever form.

Need for Further Land Reform Policy?

The challenges posed by the traditional land tenure system are enormous. Judging from the socio-economic view point, they tend to undermine economic growth and development. There arose a need for a more rational land policy to strengthen the land – human relationship, thereby facilitating development. At a time, the federal government of Nigeria was faced with pressures from various quarters concerning land reform measures. In response to those series of pressures from groups and individuals, the federal government of Nigeria in 1978 decided in favour of land reform policy and subsequently came up with a promulgation of the land use decree which vest all land in the territory of each state in the Federation in the Governor of that state, to be held in trust and administered for the use and common benefit of all Nigerians. In accordance with the provisions of the decree, all land in urban areas are to be controlled and managed by the Governor, assisted by the land use and allocation Committee, while those in rural areas are to be controlled and managed by the local government (Land Use Decree, 1978). Though land tenure reform policy as government intervention is supposed to be a design to change the land – human relationship in the society in order to redistribute land and re-model tenure rights, thereby benefiting the population (Adams, 2001), the reverse is the case in Nigeria, as land reform outcomes accrue more benefits to government at the expense of the population. This situation becomes more apparent in cases where government acquire large acreages from land holding units for agriculture and other purposes without due compensation, and subsequently breed several of landless people out of the bargain.

The Nigerian Land Use Decree of 1978 nationalised all the country and notionally handed over its administration to committee constituted at state and local government level. One justification given for this action was the rationalisation of customary land tenure systems which were held to be a constraint on agricultural development.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State Nigeria. The area was purposively chosen because majority of the people living in the area are farmers and they depend mostly on agriculture as their primary source of livelihood. Six (6) rural communities were randomly selected from the twelve (12) core rural wards/districts of the local government. From each of the six communities, twenty (20) farmers were randomly selected for the administration of questionnaire. Respondents included those who take up farming as a full time business and household heads who are custodians of lands in the area. Therefore, in all, one hundred and twenty respondents were interviewed. Data for this study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Collected data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistics such as means, percentages and frequency distributions.

Findings/Results

Table 1. Socio-economic characteristics of 120 respondents in Obio/Akpor L.G.A. Rivers State, Nigeria.

Variables/Categories	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Age		
30–39	8	6.667
40–49	19	15.833
50–59	36	30.00
60–69	40	33.333
70–79	17	14.167
Mean Years of age is 59 years		
Educational attainment		
Non literate	7	5.833
Adult education	20	16.667
Primary school	34	28.333
Secondary school	48	40.00
Tertiary education	11	9.167
Mean educational attainment is primary education		
Marital status		
Married	82	68.333
Single	38	31.667

(Source: Field survey data, 2023)

The table shows that a large proportion of the respondents (77.5%) in the study area were elderly farmers between the ages of 50 – 79 years. The mean age of the respondents was calculated to be 59 years. Ages within this range 50 – 79 are usually the ages at which people in the study area relinquish their land holdings to their children through inheritance by male heirs, which leads to constant land fragmentation in the study area.

Table 2: Various forms and characteristics of land tenure practices in the area studied.

Forms of land tenure practices in the study area	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Individual	102	85.00
Communal	2	1.667
Individual + communal	16	13.333
Methods of acquiring land		
Inheritance	18	15.00
Communal	2	1.667
Purchase	4	3.333
Inheritance + communal	12	10.00
Inheritance + purchase	50	41.667
Inheritance + lease	16	13.333
Inheritance + pledge	6	5.00
Inheritance + borrowed	8	6.667
Inheritance + sharecropping	4	3.333

(Source: Field survey data, 2023)

Table 2 shows that 85% of the respondents practiced individual holdings only. 13.333% had a combination of communal land tenure systems, while 1.667% practiced communal land tenure system only. This explains that greater than half of the respondents had full ownership of land through the prevailing land tenure system. By implication, land ownership is predominantly through inheritance and purchase. This reveals that constant transfer of land rights through inheritance led to land fragmentation thereby reducing the proportion of agricultural land area as some may use their lands for purposes other than agriculture.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution on the reasons mechanization was not practiced.

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Insufficient availability of land	48	40.00
Insufficient capital	32	26.667

Soil type	12	10.00
Lack of interest	12	10.00
Insufficient land + capital	16	13.333
Total	120	100

(Source: Field survey data, 2023)

Table 3 shows that majority of respondents did not practice mechanized farming mostly due to land fragmentation and paucity of capital. This is deduced from the data as more than half of the respondents (about 67%) are affected by the limitation. In fact, a combination of insufficient land and capital are attributable to the non-mechanisation of agricultural activities in the study area. As part of tenurial innovation, land policy reforms should consider the adoption of measures to curtail land fragmentation, while enhancing increasing farm holdings by promoting collective ownership through various community development models.

Table 4: Frequency distribution according to awareness/adoption of innovations

	Awareness of Innovations only		Awareness & adoption of Innovations	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Improved planting	17	14.167	13	10.833
Improved fertilizer And other				
Agro-chemical	13	10.833	7	5.833
Improved pesticides	9	7.5	6	5
Irrigation system Behavioural				
Increased fallow length	7	5.833	2	1.667
Other soil conservation methods				
	24	20	2	1.667
	15	12.5	5	4.167
Total	85	70.833	35	29.167

(Source: Field survey data, 2023)

Table 4 showed that 70.833% of the respondents claimed to have known or heard about one innovation or the other but due to lack of capital and access to enough land; only about (29.167%) agreed to the adoption and application of innovations. Even

land conservation that will help in the improvement and sustainability of the farmer's physical production was adopted by only four percent of the respondents.

Summary

The study reveals that a large proportion of the respondents (77.5%) are elderly farmers between the ages of 50 – 79 years. Ages within this range are usually the ages at which people in the study area relinquish their land holdings to their children through inheritance by male heirs, a behaviour which leads to constant land fragmentation in the study area.

The study also revealed that majority of respondents (about 67%) did not practice mechanized farming mostly due to land fragmentation and paucity of capital. In fact a combination of insufficient land and capital are attributable to the non-mechanization of agriculture in the study area.

Though 70.83% of the respondents claimed to have known or heard about one innovation or the other, however only about 29.17% agreed to the adoption and application of innovations. Furthermore, though majority of respondents claimed this was due to lack of capital and access to sufficient land, it is believed that lack of awareness contributed to the behaviour, as even land conservation that will help in the improvement and sustainability of the farmer's physical production was adopted by only 4% of the respondents.

Conclusion

Access to land resources has remained crucial to livelihood and household sustenance in Nigeria and other agrarian societies.

By implication, land ownership is predominantly through inheritance and purchase. This suggests the existence of regulated measure to land fragmentation which reduces the proportion of agricultural land areas through constant transfer of land right by inheritance.

The implication of the findings in this study for especially a developing economy like Nigeria is that a great limitation is placed on mechanized farming which prohibits increased agricultural productivity and threatens rural development. Farmers need to have secured land access which consequently translates to improved agricultural productivity. There is need to look into the existing land tenure systems as stipulated in the Nigerian Land use Act (LUA) of 1978 with a view to reviewing same to address the inherent issues/challenges associated with the LUA. This will consequently have a positive impact on agricultural development and productivity in the country.

Recommendation

1. The farmers should form cooperative groups so as to enable them consolidate their small scale holdings into economic size to encourage large-scale production. Such cooperative efforts can enable bulk purchase of farm inputs at reduced cost, thereby enjoying the benefit derived from economy of large scale.
2. Government should consider agricultural subvention as a means to reducing the cost of procuring farm inputs.
3. It is also important to improve on the quality of extension services in the area so as to help the farmers improve on their farm production techniques and adoption of innovations.
4. As part of tenurial innovation, land policy reforms should consider the adoption of measures to curtail land fragmentation, while enhancing increasing farm holdings by promoting collective ownership through various community development models.

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